

Tsallis and Kaniadakis Gaussian functions, applied to the analysis of Diamond Raman spectrum, and compared with Pseudo-Voigt functions

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Abstract

Previous studies (Sparavigna, 2023) have demonstrated the Tsallis q -Gaussian functions suitable for the analysis of Raman spectra. These functions can be used for simulating the different line shapes of Raman bands. Besides the q -Gaussian, another generalized Gaussian form can be investigated for Raman spectroscopy; it is the Kaniadakis κ -Gaussian probability density function, which contains the κ -exponential. Here, we consider both q - and κ -Gaussians for fitting onto the Raman spectrum of diamond. In the case of diamond, some fitting examples obtained with the Kaniadakis exponents are providing a better result, for the behavior of the far wings of the line. Comparison with pseudo-Voigt line shape is also proposed and a pseudo-Voigtian function made of a linear combination of two q -Gaussians is proposed too.

Keywords: Tsallis q -Gaussian distribution, Kaniadakis κ -Gaussian distribution, Gaussian distribution, Cauchy distribution, Lorentzian distribution, Voigt distribution, Pseudo-Voigt function, Raman spectroscopy, Diamond.

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Introduction

The q -Gaussians, also known as Tsallis functions, are probability distributions proper of the Tsallis statistics (Tsallis, 1988, 1995, Hanel et al., 2009). The q -functions are based on a generalized form of the exponential function (Sparavigna, 2022), characterized by a continuous parameter q in the range $1 < q < 3$. For q equal to 2, the q -Gaussian is the Cauchy-Lorentzian distribution (Naudts, 2009). For q close to 1, we have the usual Gaussian form. Therefore the profile of a q -Gaussian function, for $1 < q < 2$, is intermediate between that of a Gaussian function and a Lorentzian function.

Of q -Gaussians we have recently proposed the use for fitting Raman spectra (Sparavigna, 2023a,b,c,d). As clearly shown by the several examples proposed in Sparavigna, 2023c, the q -Gaussian functions are suitable for the analysis of these spectra. But besides the q -Gaussian, another generalized Gaussian form can be investigated for being used in Raman spectroscopy; it is the Kaniadakis κ -Gaussian probability density function, which contains the κ -exponential. For this generalized form of the exponential function, we have a real parameter, the κ -parameter, which is ranging from 0 to 1, that is $0 < \kappa \leq 1$. The κ -Gaussian distribution is the distribution coming from the maximization of the Kaniadakis entropy under appropriated constrain conditions (Kaniadakis, 2001, 2002, 2013).

Here, we consider both q - and κ -exponential for fitting onto the Raman spectrum of diamond, at about 1332 cm^{-1} . In the case of diamond, some fitting examples obtained with the Kaniadakis exponents are giving a better result. The pseudo-Gaussian is also considered for comparison. Before the fitting cases, some discussion is necessary. For the basic concepts and instrumentation of laser spectroscopy a reference is Demtröder, 1985.

Intermediate profile

In the analysis of Raman spectra, Lorentzian and Gaussian profiles are among the line shapes most involved in fitting the spectral band profiles. However, the line shapes of the bands usually possess an intermediate profile (Kirillov, 2004a), and therefore besides Lorentzian or Gaussian distributions, *linear combinations* (pseudo-Voigt distributions) or *convolutions* of them (Voigt distributions) are used (Meier, 2005). The Voigt convolution is obtained with the Lorentzian height weighted by a Gaussian profile.

In spectroscopy, if the emission is broadened by the radiation damping, the profile of the band is Lorentzian. This profile can be modified by different mechanisms. Among them we have the thermal broadening that introduces a Gaussian profile, with the result of a consequent Voigt profile. “Alternatively, [we can] suppose that the line is scanned by a spectrophotometer with a Gaussian sensitivity function” (Tatum, 2022). In this case we have the convolution of the line with the instrumental function profile. Let us remember that “the general expression that takes account of all the instrumentally induced distortion of the true band shape can be called the *instrument function*” (Seshadri and Jones, 1963). It is also known as the “*instrumental transfer function*” (Merlen et al., 2017).

As told in Rautian, 1958, “Each monochromatic component $\varphi(x)dx$ of the true radiation is replaced by the apparatus [instrument] function, as a result of which, at some arbitrary point x' , there is created an illumination (or current) $a(x'-x)\varphi(x)dx$. Other monochromatic components of the true distribution also make a corresponding contribution to the illumination at the point x' , and as a result the observed distribution $f(x')$ will be expressed by the following integral”:

$$f(x') = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} a(x' - x) \varphi(x) dx.$$

In the integral we have function $a(x)$ that considers “distortions both in the optical and recording parts of the apparatus” (Rautian, 1958). In Rautian, 1958, we can find several different instrumental functions that can be convoluted with the true radiation. And the true radiation can be a convolution of different broadening mechanisms. The Voigt convolution is based on Lorentzian and Gaussian profiles because the analysis starts from a Lorentzian damping model (true radiation) with a weight which is a Gaussian one. Different approaches exist (Kirillov, 2004), so that the true radiation line can be assumed different from a Lorentzian function; moreover, the weight function can be different from a pure Gaussian function. In any case, it is always necessary to determine the instrumental function profile.

In Merlen et al., 2017, researchers are telling that “If we do not take into account the instrumental transfer function that *can be negligible in many cases* (...), the total intensity of one phonon mode with a wavevector q_0 and a frequency $\omega(q_0)$, in a perfect crystal, is spread on a symmetric profile which is Lorentzian”. Between brackets (...), Merlen and coworkers tell that “If the natural width is comparable to the width of the instrumental transfer function, which is *generally* a Gaussian function, then the intensity of the band is a convolution between the natural line shape and the instrumental function. Depending on the grating used, the instrumental width varies but is in general close to 1 cm^{-1} .” Let us stress once more, that an investigation regarding the transfer function is necessary, at least to determine if it is negligible or not. The transfer function can be relevant when the decomposition (deconvolution) of the component bands is the aim of the research¹.

With its intermediate behavior, the q-Gaussian is suitable to describe convolution mechanisms in general. In Sparavigna, 2023a, we have shown that q-Gaussian is able of mimicking pseudo-Voigt and Voigt functions, and the same is true also for the Egelstaff-Schofield line shape (Sparavigna, 2023b). Besides a detailed discussion of the decomposition in bands of the Raman spectra for carbonaceous material, in

¹ For decomposition (deconvolution) of peaks, laser sources and diffraction gratings are playing a fundamental role (see the discussion in <https://www.edinst.com/blog/spectral-resolution-in-raman-spectroscopy/> for instance). “As long as the resolution is greater than the linewidth, the user will get all the information from the Raman spectrometer regardless of whether a high- or low-resolution system is used. ... The characterisation of polymorphs and crystallinity are two examples of when the user may need the highest possible resolution”.

Sparavigna, 2023c, we have shown several examples which demonstrate the q-Gaussians properly suitable for the Raman spectral data analysis. However, as told here in the Introduction, besides the q-Gaussian, another generalized Gaussian form requires to be investigated and it is the Kaniadakis κ -Gaussian probability density function, based on its κ -exponential. Here we consider the specific case of fitting the 1332 cm^{-1} peak of diamond, using both q- and κ -exponential functions. Comparison with the pseudo-Voigt line shape is also proposed, and a pseudo-Voigt made of q-Gaussians is proposed too.

In Krishnan, 1945, it is given that the Raman approach provides an atomic vibration spectrum of diamond with eight distinct monochromatic frequencies. “Of these, the highest frequency (1332 cm^{-1} in spectroscopic units) corresponds to the triply degenerate vibration of the two Bravais lattices of the carbon atoms with respect to each other, this being active in the Raman effect”.

For what is regarding the line shape, in Surovtsev and Kupriyanov, 2017, we can find that “the Raman line of diamond crystals with a negligible amount of defects can be well described by the Voigt contour, where the Gaussian component reflects the spectral resolution of the experimental setup ... and the Lorentzian component reflects the broadening caused by anharmonicity”. Discussing the role of the nitrogen defects in their article of 2017, Surovtsev and Kupriyanov show that the Voigt contour is giving better results when used *without restrictions* for the fitting parameters. Being the problem unconstrained, Tsallis and Kaniadakis line shapes are suitable for our analysis for sure.

The q- and the κ -exponential functions

Before the fit of 1332 cm^{-1} band of diamond, let us tell just some words about q- and κ -exponential functions. As given by Umarov et al., 2008, the q-Gaussian function is:

$$f(x) = C e_q(-\beta x^2),$$

where $e_q(\cdot)$ is the q-exponential function and C a scale constant. In the exponent, we use $\beta = 1/(2\sigma^2)$. The q-parameter is $1 < q < 3$. The q-exponential has the expression: $\exp_q(u) = [1 + (1 - q)u]^{1/(1-q)}$.

The κ -Gaussian contains the κ -exponential (Kaniadakis, 2013):

$$f(x) = C e_\kappa(-\beta x^2),$$

where $e_\kappa(\cdot)$ is the κ -exponential function and C a scale constant (we use $\beta = 1/(2\sigma^2)$ also in this case). The κ -parameter is greater than 0 and less or equal to 1. The κ -exponential is given as:

$$\exp_\kappa(u) = \left(\sqrt{1 + \kappa^2 u^2} + \kappa u \right)^{1/\kappa}.$$

Fitting onto 1332 cm^{-1} band

The study of the single peaks is important to understand the q- and the κ -Gaussian behaviour in the kernel and on the wings of the band. In the case of a single profile, we can easily investigate the presence of asymmetry too. Let us stress that the q- and κ -Gaussians are symmetric functions, like the Voigt function. In the following, we will fit some data from the RRUFF collection (Lafuente et al., 2015).

In the plots, data are generally given in red and the best fits in green. The misfit is also proposed in the lower part of the images. Data and best fits are given as functions of integers n (equally spaced data points and corresponding fits), for the x-axis which is representing the Raman shift. A convenient scale is used for the y-axis (intensity axis).

In Surovtsev and Kupriyanov, 2017, we can see an example of Voigt fitting in their Fig. 2. The *ratio* between the observed misfit amplitude and the high of the peak is about 0.05. This ratio can be used for comparison with our fit. As a further information, in Surovtsev and Kupriyanov, 2017, the instrumental spectral resolution is described by a Gaussian contour with a width of 0.3 cm^{-1} .

1. RRUFF ID R050205

Let us start considering diamond Raman spectra from RRUFF database. The first peak is that of RRUFF ID R050205 <https://rruff.info/diamond/display=default/R050205>, depolarized Raman spectrum (processed). Source of data is Eric Van Valkenburg. The sample is a single crystal, type IIA. The identification has been confirmed by single-crystal X-ray diffraction.

Fig. 1a: Data of RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum (processed), from 1300 to 1380 cm^{-1} . On the right, the data with log scale y-axis.

First, let us consider Gaussian and Lorentzian functions for fitting. We confirm that these functions are not able to properly fit the data, as shown by the large misfit.

Fig. 1b: The best fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum (red). On the left, Gaussians are used, Lorentzian functions on the right. Note the large misfit, given in the low parts of the plots. The reference band of misfit is assumed large 0.05, in the units of the y-axis.

Being the misfit large for Gaussian and Lorentzian functions, let us use the Tsallis q -Gaussian. The q -parameter of the q -Gaussian best fit is equal to 1.51. In the lower part of the plot, the misfit is given. The misfit is contained in the reference band, which is large 0.05 units.

Fig. 1c: Tsallis Gaussian fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum (red). The q -parameter of the q -Gaussian is equal to 1.51 (best fit). In the lower part of the plot, the misfit is given. Asymmetry seems being negligible. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (sum from $n=1$ to $n=500$). Here the fit is shown from $n=100$ to $n=400$.

Fig. 1d: On the left, four q -Gaussian fits, constrained with q equal to 1.51, 1.6, 1.7 and 1.8, are given. In red the data of RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum. The q -parameter of the q -Gaussian best fit is equal to 1.51, as given from the Fig.1c. On the right, the same plot is proposed with logarithmic scale on y-axis. Of course, the log scale is strongly enhancing the differences in the wings and the asymmetry too.

The Figure 1c is showing that the q-Gaussian is able of giving a best-fit with a low misfit. However, as shown in the Figure 1d, the use of log scale for y-axis is revealing that the best-fit q-Gaussian function ($q=1.51$) has a far-wing behaviour different from that of data (in red). Of course, we are in the region of very low values of intensity, but we can investigate if the use of the Kaniadakis form of the exponential can give a better result.

Fig. 1e: Kaniadakis Gaussian fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum (red). The κ -parameter of the κ -Gaussian is equal to 0.76 (best fit). In the lower part of the plot, the misfit is given. Note that the misfit is lower than that observed in the Figure 1c (q-Gaussian).

In the Figure 1e, we can see that the best fit obtained using the Kaniadakis exponential is giving a better result, as shown by its misfit. The Kaniadakis Gaussian misfit is reduced with respect the Tsallis Gaussian misfit.

Fig. 1f: Two fits with constrained κ -parameters equal to 0.76 and 0.9. In red the data of RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum. The κ -parameter of the κ -Gaussian best-fit is equal to 0.76, as given from the Fig.1e. Note the log scale on y-axis. The fit of the far wings is quite better in this case, where a Kaniadakis Gaussian has been used.

Fig. 1g: Fit with κ -parameter equal to 0.76 from $n=1$ to $n=500$, that is, all the data used for the fit.

In the Figures 1d and 1f,1g, we have used a log scale for y-axis (intensity axis). The range is from 0.001 to 1 and from 0.0001 to 1. In the Figure 2 by Surovtsev and Kupriyanov, 2017, the plot with y-axis log scale shows data ranging from about 0.3 to 27 in intensity. For comparison, let us give the plot with the same *visual effect* proposed by Surovtsev and Kupriyanov. In the following figure, the result is given.

Fig. 1h: Kaniadakis Gaussian fit (κ -parameter equal to 0.76). In red the data of RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum. The fit of the far wings is proposed with the same visual effect, as in Surovtsev and Kupriyanov.

We have seen the fit of Tsallis and Kaniadakis Gaussians onto RRUFF data. However, we know that for fitting the behavior of a line shape, which is intermediate between those of the Gaussian and Lorentzian line functions, Voigt functions are used too. For the sake of simplicity, let us consider the most used approximation of the Voigt function, that is the pseudo-Voigt function (linear combination of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions). In the following plot, the best fit with pseudo-Voigt is given.

Fig. 1i: On the left, pseudo-Voigt fit (green). In red the data of RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum. On the right, the same plot is proposed with log scale on y-axis. In the following plot, comparison with q -Gaussian and κ -Gaussian is given.

Fig. 1j: Data in red. The best fit is that given by the Kaniadakis Gaussian. The sum of the squares of the deviations (from $n=1$ to $n=500$) is equal to 5.5×10^{-3} . For the pseudo-Voigt (blue), we have 8.3×10^{-3} . For the q -Gaussian we find 1.06×10^{-2} (magenta).

2. RRUFF ID R050205 (Lorentzian component)

In the Fig. 1j, we considered the behavior of pseudo-Voigtian fit. It is obtained by a linear combination of a Gaussian and a Lorentzian function. Here, we have the occasion to consider the behavior of the Kaniadakis exponential in the fit onto Lorentzian functions.

Fig. 2a: The Lorentzian (red) and the Gaussian (green) components of the pseudo-Voigt in the Figs. 1i and 1j.

Let us consider the Lorentzian component (in red in the Fig. 2a) and compare it to a κ -Gaussian function. In the following plots, on the left, we can see the Lorentzian fitted by a κ -Gaussian in the case of its κ -parameter equal to 1; on the right it is proposed the best fit, which is giving a value of κ -parameter of 1.19.

Fig. 2b: A Lorentzian function (red) is compared to a κ -Gaussian function. On the left, the κ -Gaussian parameter is equal to 1. On the right it is proposed the best fit, with κ -parameter equal to 1.19.

Using a κ -exponential function, to have the best-fit of a Lorentzian function we need the κ -parameter larger than 1. In the case of the Tsallis function, the q -Gaussian for q equal to 2 is precisely the Lorentzian function. The behavior shown above tell us that we need to devote a future work about the κ -Gaussian fitting onto quasi-Lorentzian peaks. This work is fundamental for investigations where the aim is the decomposition of the Raman spectrum.

3. RRUFF ID R050205 (raw data)

Another test that we can do on RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum is that of considering the raw data. Let us use them as in the following figure, where we calculated a local linear baseline (the same we did in the case of the Figure 12.2 in Sparavigna, 2023c).

Fig. 3a: Data from RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum (raw, with a local linear baseline). On the right, the data with log scale y-axis.

Fig. 3b: Best-fit with κ -parameter equal to 0.74, from $n=1$ to $n=400$.

Changing the base lines slightly influences the values of q - or κ -parameters.

4. RRUFF ID R050205 (zero degrees)

Let us consider also, in the case of RRUFF ID R050205, the Raman spectrum recorded with a direction of 0° of the laser polarization relative to the fiducial mark. Let us use the processed data.

Fig. 4a: Tsallis Gaussian fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205, polarized 0° Raman spectrum (red). The sum of the squares of the deviations is equal to 1.89×10^{-2} .

Fig. 4b: Kaniadakis Gaussian fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205, polarized 0° Raman spectrum (red). The sum of the squares of the deviations is equal to 1.76×10^{-2} .

Fig. 4c: Pseudo-Voigt fit onto RRUFF ID R050205, polarized 0° Raman spectrum. The sum of the squares of the deviations is equal to 2.12×10^{-2} .

Fig. 4d: Fits onto RRUFF ID R050205, polarized 0° Raman spectrum. Here we have added the fit with pseudo-Voigt obtained by means of Fityk software (Wojdyr, 2010). In this case, the sum of the squares of deviations is equal to 3.25×10^{-2} .

Fig. 4e: Fits onto RRUFF ID R050205, polarized 0° Raman spectrum. Here we have added the fit with Voigt function obtained by means of Fityk software (Wojdyr, 2010). For Fityk Voigt, the sum of the squares of deviations is equal to 2.49×10^{-2} .

In the Figures 4d and 4e we can see the far wings being better represented by the Voigt and pseudo-Voigt function. But the far wings have intensity values which are very low. Therefore, in the sum of the squares of deviations the role of the far wings has a scarce relevance. It is the role of kernel and near wings which dominates. The study of Tsallis and Kaniadakis functions is therefore relevant to investigate the decomposition of the Raman spectra, where the far wings of the component bands are merged into a contribution which is difficult to separate.

5. RRUFF ID R050206

Let us consider processed data of RRUFF R050206 depolarized Raman spectrum. As for the previous sample, the source is Eric Van Valkenburg. The sample is a single crystal, type IIA, identified also by single-crystal X-ray diffraction. Let us start investigation with the Raman data as they are given in the following Fig.5a. Then we will investigate what is happening if we assume a *shift* of the baseline, to have the zero intensity at a specifically given onset of the peak.

Fig. 5a: Data from RRUFF ID R050206 <https://rruff.info/diamond/display=default/R050206> depolarized Raman spectrum (processed). On the right, the data with log scale y-axis. Let us assume the onset of the peak at $n=100$.

Fig. 5b: Tsallis Gaussian fit (green, q -parameter of q -Gaussian is equal to 1.31) onto the data from RRUFF ID R050206 depolarized, as in the Fig.5a. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from $n=100$ to $n=430$). The sum of the squares of deviations is 1.67×10^{-2} . There is a small asymmetry, and we can stress this fact using a log scale for the y-axis. As before, remember that the visual effect of the log scale on far wings is rendering a very small intensity difference in a huge gap.

Fig. 5c: Pseudo-Voigt fit (green) onto the data from RRUFF ID R050206 depolarized, as in the Fig. 5a. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from $n=100$ to $n=430$). The sum of the squares of deviations is 1.16×10^{-2} .

Fig. 5d: Fityk Pseudo-Voigt fit (green) onto the data from RRUFF ID R050206 depolarized. The sum of the squares of the deviations (from $n=100$ to $n=430$) is equal to 1.46×10^{-2} .

Fig. 5e: Kaniadakis Gaussian fit (green) onto the data from RRUFF ID R050206 depolarized. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from $n=100$ to $n=430$). The sum of the squares of deviations is 1.28×10^{-2} . The κ -parameter is equal to 0.56.

Here we would like to consider a specific problem in the fitting procedure. Let us suppose a shift of the baseline, so that to have zero intensity at the data point $n=100$, assuming it as the onset of the peak. With the q -Gaussian we have the following result.

Fig. 5f: Tsallis Gaussian fit (green, q -parameter of q -Gaussian is equal to 1.27) onto the data from RRUFF ID R050206, depolarized (red), shifted to have the zero intensity at datapoint $n=100$ (blue points). As before, consider the visual effect of the log scale on far wings.

Let us consider the Kaniadakis Gaussians. The result is given in the following figure.

Fig. 5g: Best Kaniadakis Gaussian fit (green, κ -parameter of κ -Gaussian is equal to 0.5) onto the data from RRUFF ID R050206, depolarized (red), shifted to have zero intensity at datapoint $n=100$ (blue points). Once more, consider the visual effect of the log scale on far wings: the result seems to be better than that obtained with the q -Gaussian.

6. RRUFF ID X050052 and others

ID X050052 is a diamond from Plumas County, California, USA. Source and Owner is Caltech. Identification of the mineral has been determined only by Raman spectroscopy. The analysis has been made by a de-polarized laser on unoriented sample (laser 785nm @ 100% of mW).

In the following figures, we can find the data and the best fit with Tsallis and Kaniadakis Gaussians. We use the processed data (without any adjustment).

Fig. 6a: Data RRUFF ID X050052 <https://rruff.info/diamond/display=default/X050052> Raman spectrum (red).

Fig. 6b: The best Tsallis fit (green) onto RRUFF ID X050052 Raman spectrum (red). The q -parameter of the q -Gaussian is equal to 1.416. In the lower part of the plots, the misfit is given. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from $n=150$ to $n=400$). Here the fit is shown from $n=150$ to $n=380$.

Fig. 6c: The best Kaniadakis fit (green) onto RRUFF ID X050052 Raman spectrum (red). The κ -parameter of the κ -Gaussian is equal to 0.675. In the lower part of the plots, the misfit is given. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from $n=150$ to $n=400$). Here the fit is shown from $n=150$ to $n=380$.

Fig. 6d: The best Kaniadakis fit (green) onto RRUFF ID X050052 Raman spectrum (red), proposed with a different visual effect.

Let us continue considering RRUFF R050204 depolarized, RRUFF R050207 depolarized, RRUFF X050053 depolarized, <https://rruff.info/Diamond/R050204> , <https://rruff.info/Diamond/R050207> , <https://rruff.info/diamond/display=default/X050053> processed data. Only the fit with Kaniadakis Gaussians is considered.

Fig. 6e: The best Kaniadakis fit (green) onto RRUFF ID 050204 Raman spectrum (red). The κ -parameter of the κ -Gaussian is equal to 0.51. In the lower part of the plots, the misfit is given. As in the previous cases, the band is 0.05 wide. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from 0 to 470).

Fig. 6f: The best Kaniadakis fit (green) onto RRUFF ID X050053 Raman spectrum (red). The κ -parameter of the κ -Gaussian is equal to 0.86. In the lower part of the plots, the misfit is given. As in the previous cases, the band is 0.05 wide. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from 50 to 500).

Fig. 6g: The best Kaniadakis fit (green) onto RRUFF ID 050207 Raman spectrum (red). The κ -parameter of the κ -Gaussian is equal to 0.54. In the lower part of the plots, the misfit is given. As in the previous cases, the band is 0.05 wide. The fitting calculation is obtained by minimizing the sum of the squares of the deviations (from 0 to 470).

7. Generalizing the pseudo-Voigt

In the previous data analysis, we considered besides the q - and the κ -Gaussian functions the pseudo-Voigt functions. The pseudo-Voigtians are a linear combination of two base functions, which are Gaussian and Lorentzian functions. We could also consider generalizing the combination, using a base made of q -Gaussian functions. That is, we use a linear combination of two q -Gaussians. Let us stress that the q -parameter is $1 < q < 3$. Here in the following some examples.

Fig. 7a: Linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum (red). The q -parameters of the q -Gaussians are equal to 1.792 (blue) and 1.175 (magenta). The fitting calculation is made by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (from 1 to 500). This sum is equal to 5.85×10^{-3} . For comparison, see Fig.1j.

From the Fig.7a, we can appreciate that the kernel is mainly made by the q -Gaussian component which is Gaussian-like ($q=1.166$), whereas the wings are given by the q -Gaussian with Lorentzian-like character ($q=1.775$).

Fig. 7b: As before, linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205 depolarized Raman spectrum (red). In the lower part of the figure, the misfit is given.

Let us consider the sample R050205 with a direction of 0° of the laser polarization relative to the fiducial mark.

Fig. 7c: Linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205 zero degrees Raman spectrum (red). The q -parameters of the q -Gaussians are equal to 1.833 (blue) and 1.300 (magenta). The fitting calculation is made by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (from 1 to 500). This sum is equal to 1.74×10^{-2} . For comparison, see Fig. 4d.

Fig. 7d: As in the Fig. 7c, linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050205 zero degrees Raman spectrum (red). In the lower part of the figure, the misfit is given.

Fig. 7e: Linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID R050206 depolarized Raman spectrum (red). The q -parameters of the q -Gaussians are equal to 1.85 (blue) and 1.033 (magenta) The fitting calculation is made by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (from 100 to 430). The sum of the squares of deviations is 1.14×10^{-2} . For comparison, Fig. 5c and 5d. In the lower part of the figure, the misfit is given.

Fig. 7f: Linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID X050052 depolarized Raman spectrum (red). The q -parameters of the q -Gaussians are equal to 1.775 (blue) and 1.075 (magenta) The fitting calculation is made by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (from 1 to 650). The sum of the squares of deviations is 2.58×10^{-3} .

Fig. 7g: As in the Fig. 7f, linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID X050052 Raman spectrum (red). In the lower part of the figure, the misfit is given.

We have seen in previous examples that, in the linear combination of q-Gaussians, the q-parameters are less than 2. The following case is interesting because we can find a q-parameter greater than 2. In this case we will provide the comparison with pseudo-Voigt and Fityk pseudo-Voigt fits.

Fig. 7h: Linear combination of Tsallis Gaussians fit (green) onto RRUFF ID 050204 Raman spectrum (red). The q-parameters of the best-fit q-Gaussians are equal to **2.67** (blue) and 1.01 (magenta) The fitting calculation is made by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (from 1 to 470). The sum of the squares of deviations is 7.53×10^{-3} .

Fig. 7i: Pseudo-Voigt fit (green) onto RRUFF ID 050204 Raman spectrum (red). The q -parameters of the q -Gaussians are equal to **2.0** (blue) and **1.01** (magenta). The fitting calculation is made by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (from 1 to 470). The sum of the squares of deviations is 8.57×10^{-3} .

Fig. 7j: Pseudo-Voigt Fityk fit (green) onto RRUFF ID 050204 Raman spectrum (red). The fitting calculation is made by minimizing the sum of the squares of deviations (from 1 to 470). The sum of the squares of deviations is 1.93×10^{-2} .

Remarks

- 1) In general, an iterative approach to fit (gradient methods, Newton methods, Marquardt-Levenberg algorithms) is designed to find a local optimum. In the space of the parameter values, an initial set of them is chosen, and a local minimum of the sum of the squares of deviations determined. It is better to vary the initial set to test the opportunity of other minima.
- 2) We have shown that Tsallis Gaussians, Kaniadakis Gaussians and pseudo-Voigt functions are providing slightly different results. It is necessary to know the transfer function of the instrument to determine if it is possible to discriminate the results and decide the preferred function. It is also necessary to consider the manner the data have been processed and the role of the baseline. Without any information regarding processing, the Tsallis Gaussian fitting examples provided in Sparavigna, 2023c, show that we can use these functions to substitute pseudo-Voigt and Voigt functions.
- 3) The log scale is enhancing the far-wing behaviour and this is relevant for distinguishing Kaniadakis Gaussians from Tsallis Gaussians and pseudo-Voigt functions. We can appreciate that the far-wings of Kaniadakis Gaussians, pseudo-Voigt and Voigt functions are more “Lorentzian” than those of the Tsallis Gaussians. “Voigt function looks like Gaussian for small x (i.e., near line center), and like Lorentzian for large x (i.e., out in line wings)” (Townsend, 2008).
- 4) When observing data and fits provided in the figures of publications, please carefully consider the scale of the plots and the *visual effect*.
- 5) As previously told, the role of the baseline is fundamental, but about baseline, information is impossible to recover from the simple inspection of images in publications. The same is true for the instrument transfer function.
- 6) To use Kaniadakis functions, further studies are necessary as those proposed in Sparavigna, 2023c.

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